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Digital Learning Literacy Preference and Accessibility of Universitas Terbuka (UT)'s SUAKA-UT: An Evaluation towards Its System of Open Educational Resource (OER)

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Abstract

This article aims to analyze the preference and accessibility that determine the students' behavioural appreciation in using learning resources towards the Open Educational Resources (OER) system owned by the Universitas Terbuka (UT), a so-called SUAKA-UT. It used qualitative research methods with descriptive percentage analysis. Furthermore, the instrument employed a Sakal Likert questionnaire and limited interviews. The research population was a non-basic educational program, with the random sampling technique by selecting 123 students. The following sample details: 35 students in Makassar City, 19 Students in Sidrap Regency, 23 students in Tana Toraja Regency, 23 Students in Selayar Regency, and 23 students in Luwu Timur Regency. The results showed that the preference for online sources and accessibility is in the excellent category and had an average score of 4.10 out of ten SUAKA-UT service questions. They showed that, generally, the respondents strongly agree with the available learning resources since they can meet the needs and accessibility of online learning resources. Preference for online learning resources is a supporting tool for achieving independent learning success. The utilization of SUAKA-UT in the working area of UT Makassar went very well in providing easy access to learning resources. The UT has met students' needs and expectations so they can study flexibly. SUAKA-UT has become a preferred and has excellent acceptance as an online learning resource among the students. To maintain the existence of open learning sources of UT (SUAKA-UT), as a distance learning university with the motto of "Making Higher education," it must consistently innovate and update its online learning resources.

Keywords: SUAKA-UT, Online Learning Resources, Flexible

1. Introduction

As a state university, Universitas Terbuka (UT) provides access to higher education for all levels of society through the implementation of various Distance Open Higher Education programs. To produce graduates with good competitiveness, UT has developed innovations related to the quality of educational products and online academic

services. Learning technology at UT can adapt to changing times following developments, becoming a benchmark for distance education providers and becoming a leader towards cyber university. In this regard, UT's open learning source, so-called SUAKA-UT, is an Open Educational Resources (OER) (accessible through <http://www.ut.ac.id/OER/index.html>) containing online-based enrichment materials. They include UT Television, UT Radio, Online Smart Teachers, UT Journal, MOOCS, ASEAN Studies Program, and Digital Libraries that provide learning materials that students and the wider community can access for free. SUAKA-UT provides a variety of quality learning resource materials made by the lecturers, either individually or in teams, by adopting a creative commons license (link: <http://www.creativecommons.org>). Its materials use the CCBY-NC-SA license. Its benefit is that it can help students improve mastery of the learning material by freely utilizing learning resources to encourage students to become strong independent learners.

SUAKA-UT's contributions to the Open Education Consortium's Learning Resources include the UT Library Service Center, with quite diverse library materials consisting of a Virtual Reading room and Online-Based Material Enrichment in the form of videos. In it, students can access course enrichment, interactive videos, dry lab, radio programs, television programs, material enrichment and independent online exercises, and UT TV. The UT has a collection of learning materials in videos that can be accessed by online streaming. According to the faculty and student majors, the study materials are divided into several categories. SUAKA-UT's variety includes 1) UT Radio, which is the UT's internet radio pride; 2) the Central Web-UT, containing various types to support the needs of students, both administrative and academic needs; and 3) Online independent exercise, where students can directly access questions under the subjects being studied, aiming to measure and find out the level of mastery of the subject matter before facing the final semester exam. Furthermore, the UT open course is an online-based enrichment of primary material and a virtual reading room with primary material to be used anywhere to improve students' mastery of the material.

The development and use of open education resources (OER) are rapidly increasing in various countries' higher education institutions (HEIs) (Mtebe & Raisamo, 2014). Access to these resources is expanded, reduces costs, and can improve the quality of education. Utilizing the aforementioned UT-online learning resources is a preference with various variants of online service activities. Preferences for measuring the usability of online learning materials, from which students take advantage of UT-online service resources as an option that can motivate them to increase their independent spirit in the learning process. The availability of UT-online services allows students to meet their learning needs to achieve the desired learning goals. Preferences shape behaviour and perceptions of using learning resources at UT-online regarding perceived benefits. Preference when interpreted is a choice of liking or disliking UT-online learning resources. Student decisions in utilizing online learning resource facilities, student preferences in utilizing online services, and the level of participation in their use continue to increase based on questionnaires and limited interviews. Students have a good preference for using SUAKA-UT to improve mastery of the material to support academic activities. The accessibility or ease of accessing online learning resources is determined by how students access learning resources available at SUAKA-UT. Online learning resources can use facilities such as mobile phones (with an android system) or laptop, which has a network to access online learning resources. The increase in its utilization results from new student study orientation and distance learning skills training, which socialize and train them to use online learning resources.

The UT-online facility, related to one of the research findings with an average score of 4.1 in the excellent category, helps improve the quality of student academic services. Sugilar et al. (2014) explained that the utilization of UT-online resources, and its facilities based on the number of users, frequency of users, and length of access, was assessed with a positive score. UT Makassar has maximized socialization for students to participate in new student study orientation and distance learning skills training so that students are more skilled in accessing and utilizing SUAKA-UT to achieve independent learning success. The students' preferences emphasize students' attitudes to using and utilizing online learning resources as an alternative based on pleasure, satisfaction, fulfillment, and usefulness. They enable students to achieve the desired learning goals and increase accessibility to the use of online resources to support learning activities according to their learning targets. Easy access to online learning materials allows students to use teaching materials wherever and whenever they are. Such ease of accessing learning resources to improve student mastery of the material before taking final exams is vital. By knowing the conditions of students' preferences and accessibility in utilizing SUAKA-UT resources, the students are increasingly

motivated to use it as a learning mode that supports the success of distance education students at UT Makassar spread over 24 districts in South Sulawesi. Student learning activities through SUAKA-UT help those living in remote areas and islands improve mastery of primary materials in preparation for their final exams. Based on these backgrounds, this article intends to answer the research question of "how could the students take advantage of SUAKA-UT as UT's online learning resource services by combining printed teaching materials with online blended learning to support their successful learning?". This article assesses student preferences and accessibility in using online learning resources (SUAKA-UT) by taking samples from the outermost points of UT Makassar, namely the Selayar Islands, East Luwu, and Tana Toraja Regency. Although there are several similar previous studies in other UT units, the research differs in sampling and data collection techniques. It used questionnaires and limited interviews to explore further the facilities, as well as the obstacles experienced by students. This article is expected to become an input for policy making regarding the socialization of using online learning resources at UT Makassar.

2. Literature Review

2.1 *The Open Learning Resources of UT (SUAKA-UT)*

Students who study with the distance education system must be independent in solving all their problems. This learning model is required for the students to learn independently. Furthermore, distance education providers are required to provide learning assistance services. Study assistance for distance learning students in all forms of assistance given to students so that their study process runs smoothly, starting from registration, study process, during exams and even when they finish exams. In a narrow sense, learning assistance services are services provided by education providers to students in studying teaching materials or during the learning process. Services in studying teaching materials are often called tutorials.

In accessing tutoring and independent online practice, UT students must have facilities or tools connected to the internet network. Facilities that can be used include mobile phones based on the android system. Almost everyone has had it as a communication device, making it easy for students to access the UT-online service page from various places where internet networks are available. Student access to UT-online has a significant relationship or influence with the level and variation of student accessibility, starting from the lowest, medium, and high levels. The level of student accessibility depends on each student's activity (Wahyuningsih Suharmini Sri et al., 2014).

Quality and affordability are challenges for today's higher education success. Low-cost open educational resources (OER) can increase students' final grades. It presents a multifunctional medium in the learning process (Colvard, Watson, & Park, 2018). Communication via the internet can be done interpersonally or en masse, known as one-to-many communication. The internet can also be present in real-time audio-visual as with the conventional teleconference application. Based on this, the internet as an educational medium can present distinctive characteristics, such as (a) interpersonal and mass media, (b) interactive (c) allowing synchronous and asynchronous communication (Hariyono, 2015). The OER, a term agreed upon by various organizations, including UNESCO, is defined as teaching materials or research results available in open media sharing (applying for an open license) and free of charge to be accessed, reused or adapted and redistributed by users. It is usually in textbooks, curriculum, syllabus, notes, sample assignments, sample tests provided in audio format, video tutorials or animations. Nascimbeni & Burgos (2019) explain that it covers the creation, use, and reuse of open educational resources, open pedagogy, and the open sharing of teaching practices. Teaching materials in OER are often also called digital internet-based or web-based teaching materials. Lestari et al. (2015) expose that three main characteristics constitute the great potential of online teaching materials: presenting multimedia, storing, processing, and presenting information and hyperlinks. Because of its online nature, web-based teaching materials have unique characteristics according to the characteristics of the web itself and help students improve student achievement. From a constructivist perspective, OER's conceptual model suggests four characteristic dimensions: balancing privacy and openness, developing digital literacy, valuing social learning, and challenging traditional teaching role expectations.

2.2 Accessibility of UT-Online Learning Resources

According to Kamus Besar Bahasa Indonesia (KBBI) or the Indonesian Language Master Dictionary, "access" is a way to enter and continue. Further referring to multiple journals means the degree of ease people achieve towards an object, service, or environment. Furthermore, accessibility is the ease of accessing destinations that provide comfort for activities (Wahyuningsih, 2015). So that users or students can find what they need quickly, precisely and on target. In this case, information and communication technology (ICT) is very helpful in finding the information needed. The development of the internet network that has penetrated regions and islands such as in Selayar Regency makes it easier for students to find and access the SUAKA-UT. Ease of access can influence student participation in learning through internet media. Accessibility in the UT's distance learning relates to the availability and ease of obtaining or using online learning resources. It is a measure of convenience with online learning resources interacting easily through a network system with available service access procedures. Furthermore, it measures ease, including time, cost, and effort in using UT-online learning resources. The high or low levels of accessibility can be determined by the available network facilitating accessibility to them. Additionally, Wahyuningsih, Rusli, & Bintarti (2015) investigate student accessibility in tutoring and the relationship of accessibility to tutoring with learning evaluation (final exams). They found that the convenience for students in using online tutorial services can help them understand the learning material provided and help students get the final semester exam scores as expected.

2.3 SUAKA-UT Learning Resources Constituting Student Preferences

The consumer preferences show the likeliness inclination of consumers from the choice of products or services that exist in their perception. The preferences will determine a person's behaviour towards a service or facility. The choice of someone's likes or dislikes for products or service facilities is to be used to fulfil their needs. The factors that influence student preferences for using online facilities provided in SUAKA-UT will describe the factors that influence the students of non-basic education programs. The learning assistance services at SUAKA-UT provide online services to students, covering Online-Based Tutorials, so-called Tuton, independent online practice, online-based material enrichment, and radio tutorial. In detail, Tuton is provided that individual students get special access differently from other students. This feature could be accessed through "learning.ut.ac.id". It provides tutoring facilities in line with course registration carried out by students during the ongoing semester. Besides Tuton, SUAKA-UT also provides independent online practice. It is hidden or not directly visible on the UT's web home page. It can be accessed through "http://student.ut.ac.id/repository/." It aims to determine student understanding of the module material through the number of questions answered correctly and incorrectly. It does not have a contribution to the final score. Still, if the students are diligent in practising through it, they can improve their ability to understand module material, which has an impact on increasing their academic achievement. As a supplement to student academic success, UT also provides "web-supplement.ut.ac.id" or online-based material enrichment, an integral part of the student's primary material. It contains the main points and essential concepts of basic materials per course. With more diverse student learning resources, the student will have more preference in choosing and accessing the learning resources provided by UT. UT also provides radio tutorials through National Program 1 of Radio of the Republic of Indonesia (RRI) on FM 92.8 MHz, MW 1332 kHz and SW 9680 kHz at 14.35 – 15.00 WIB. This radio tutorial is held six times a week, Monday to Saturday. Especially for teachers, TV tutorials can be watched via TM Education channel 2. It is broadcasted via Telkom I satellite with a satellite dish directed to Horizontal Polarization with the broadcast frequency of 3807 MHz and Downlink 3807 MHz. It is also broadcasted via Symbol Rate (SR) 400 on Saturday from 14.00 – 16.00 Western Indonesia Time (WIB) and via satellite on the SWARA channel from Monday to Sunday from 05.00 – 05.30 WIB.

All UT educational menus, whether informational or service, are included on the UT website. Its online services have followed the development of information technology in the modern era. Direct access to UT services, which contains a list of UT's services, can be undertaken using an Android-based cellphone or laptop with an online network. SUAKA-UT provides many menus of learning assistance services for students to support the success of independent learning, which is the hallmark and character of students undertaking distance education programs.

3. Method and Methodology

3.1 Types of research

This type of research is descriptive qualitative percentage research. It is a research technique of collecting data using a questionnaire instrument to generate primary data sources and using limited interviews to picture SUAKA-UT utilization directly. The data and its frequency are managed, simplified, and presented to provide an orderly picture of an event that can be expressed in numbers. The discussion will refer to the results of the Likert scale questionnaire and will refer to limited interview information obtained from respondents.

3.2 Population and Sample

3.2.1 Population

In this study, the population was all non-basic education program students at UT Makassar who registered in 2017 and 2018. The students are assumed to have followed the new student study orientation, attended self-study skills training, and understood the online learning resources provided by the UT.

3.2.2 Sample

The random sampling technique was used in determining random samples based on the area (random cluster sampling). In it, the population does not consist of individuals. However, it consists of regional groups or district clusters in this research, consisting of 35 students in Makassar City, 23 students in Selayar Regency, 19 students in Sidrap Regency, 23 students in Tana Toraja Regency, and 23 students in East Luwu Regency. There are five clusters with 123 students—the cluster samples were chosen randomly from the cluster population.

3.3 Data source

The data source is an essential factor that is considered in determining the data collection method. Data sources in this article were obtained from primary and secondary data. The primary data was obtained directly from the respondents by providing questionnaires and interviews. Data sources are more emphasized for students who have access to online learning resources. Meanwhile, the secondary data was obtained from limited interviews to complete a questionnaire about the complete picture of the utilization of SUAKA-UT.

3.4 Data Collection Method

The data collection method used in this study is a survey method to collect data using a Likert scale questionnaire. A survey (or self-administered survey) collected primary data by giving questions to individual respondents. The interview method was aimed at students who have already used SUAKA-UT, course enrichment materials, and radio tutorials. The type of interview used was limited to support quantitative data related to SUAKA-UT.

3.5 Data Analysis Method and Flows

In this study, descriptive frequency analysis was used with the tool used to find the relationship between variables was software SPSS 15 for windows. Meanwhile, the data analysis flows to facilitate data analysis was ordered as follows: The author surveyed respondents whom the author had determined. Then, after the data from the respondents were collected, the authors tabulated the data by entering data from the respondents into Microsoft Excel. Then after the data were entered into it, the writer processed the data using SPSS 15 using descriptive analysis of frequencies. Therefore, it generated data for preferences and accessibility in the number of per cent (%) of SUAKA-UT usage.

3. Results

The results show a significant change in the use of online learning resources. Students take advantage of the facilities, have understood the access procedure, and know the benefits of online learning resources. The frequency of students using online learning resources available at SUAKA-UT contributes to learning success. Accessibility to online learning resources for students is getting better. Using these online learning resources is an initiative and responsibility of the students to independently learn, research, solve the problem, and absorb material to increase a comprehensive understanding of the course's core educational material or modules. Students' flexibility in managing their learning patterns reflects their ability to adapt to how distance education students learn. The learning resources provided by UT are very diverse and online-based to ensure adaptation to the era of ICT disruption. The Ministry of Research and Higher Education prioritizes fields of study to be able to absorb the benefits of the rapid development of technology and information. The development of the internet network has changed the paradigm of education and learning in obtaining varied information and communication, which is no longer being limited by the dimensions of space and time in the learning process. Specifically, the research data collection, reflecting the educational dynamics usage of UT's online learning resources (SUAKA-UT), was carried out in Makassar City and Sidrap, Tanah Toraja, Selayar, and East Luwu regencies. The number of each respondent is as shown in the following table (in general, it has been close to a proportional number in each region):

Table: 1 Frequency of Respondents of SUAKA-UT Open Learning Resources Utilization

No	Instrument	Scale				Total	Average
		<i>Dislike</i>	<i>Neutral</i>	<i>Like</i>	<i>Very Like</i>		
1	Varied online learning resources	3	18	65	37	123	4.11
2	Easy access to UT-online as an affordable and valuable source of student learning	1	9	62	51	123	4.32
3	Preference for UT-Online learning resources is very helpful for students' academic success	0	18	80	25	123	4.06
4	The UT-online learning resource page is interesting because it provides various means to support learning activities.	0	19	83	21	123	4.02
5	The influence of literacy to support the learning process at UT	0	23	71	29	123	4.04
6	The material presented is up to date.	2	22	62	37	123	4.11
7	Help improve material mastery.	1	23	68	31	123	4.06
8	UT-online learning accessibility is very beneficial for students and the general public.	0	12	80	31	123	4.15
9	Online independent practice helps students self-evaluate the value of learning achievement.	0	13	84	26	123	4.11
10	A digital library (virtual reading room) helps to support learning activities.	4	19	70	30	123	3.99
11	UT-online provides TV and radio learning content that students need.	1	17	68	37	123	4.14
12	The enrichment material for the web supplement course helps improve mastery of the material.	0	17	86	20	123	4.02

Source: Primary Data processed 2019.

Based on Table 1. above, the respondents were 123 students. They can be described as follows;

1. Varied online learning resources: the average of the overall scores resulted in 4.11, which means, in general, it can be stated that respondents strongly agree that the learning resources available in online learning resources are varied,
2. Easy access to UT-online as an affordable and valuable source of student learning: the average of the overall scores resulted in 4.32. In general, it can be stated that respondents strongly agree that learning resources are easily available and accesibble.
3. UT-Online learning resources reference is very helpful for students' academic success: the average of the overall scores resulted in 4.06. In general, it can be stated strongly agree to make preference or choice of learning resources.
4. The UT-online learning resource page is interesting because it provides various means to support learning activities. The average of the overall scores resulted in 4.02.
5. The influence of literacy to support the learning process at UT with a score of 4.04 responded very well. In general, it can be stated that respondents strongly agree with the learning resources available in online learning resources.
6. The material presented is up to date with a score of 4.11, meaning that the material follows the needs and developments. Generally, it can be stated that the respondents strongly agree with the currently available learning resources.
7. Help improve the mastery of the material score of 4.06, which means that in general, it can be stated that the respondents strongly agree with the learning resources available in online learning resources.
8. UT-online learning accessibility is very beneficial for students and the general public, with a score of 4.15. In general, it can be stated that respondents strongly agree that the available learning resources are easily accessible.
9. Online self-evaluation helps students with self-evaluation with a score of 4.11. In general, it can be stated that respondents strongly agree with online self-evaluation exercises for mastery of the material.
10. The digital library helps to support learning activities with a score of 3.99. The response was very well to the digital library. In general, it can be stated that the respondents strongly agree that learning resources are available online learning resources.
11. UT-online provides TV and radio. The learning content needed by students scores 4.14, which means that, generally, the respondents strongly agree with the learning resources available in online learning resources.
12. The enrichment material for the web-supplement course helps improve the mastery of the material with a score of 4.02, which means that, in general, the enrichment of online material is very agreeable as an online learning resource.

So that the average of 12 items, the overall score produces a score of 4.1. In general, it can be stated that the respondents responded strongly agree that SUAKA-UT online learning resources are excellent.

4. Discussion

Based on the respondents' answers, several criteria indicate that SUAKA-UT has been socialized through various activities such as new student orientation and distance learning skills training. They have led to increased students' ability and digital literacy to take advantage of the online learning resources provided by UT. Ghofur & Wahjoedi (2018) explained that the increasingly diverse online learning resources give students more active and fun learning choices. However, this is also determined by the preferences and abilities of students in choosing the right online learning resources. Iswanto (2021) further explained that the socialization of online learning that is not optimal for institutional leaders and users could affect students' preferences and abilities in choosing the right learning resources. The availability of free and open materials found by the library still needs to be sought intensively by users who have not experienced OER services at the library.

This study further shows that students' preferences for online learning resources are excellent. All respondents from East Luwu Regency, Makassar City, Selayar Regency, and Sidrap Regency indicated that they preferred

SUAKA-UT as an online learning resource. The results of this study align with Sugilar's (2014) research that UT-Online, an online-based student learning service provided to all students with various characteristics and knowledge, shows an increase in its utilization. Student accessibility to UT online learning resources benefits students and the general public. Mardiana & Surahman (2022) explained that student accessibility needs to be improved by increasing digital literacy. It can be done by providing knowledge about how to access the internet safely and healthily and the ability to identify which applications and smartphones are good and wise for them to use. Easy access to SUAKA-UT using mobile devices and laptops helps students combine online learning resources with basic materials to help students utilize various supporting facilities to support learning success.

Based on the survey results, the ease of accessing UT-online as an affordable and valuable source of student learning averages 4.32 (excellent). It is the choice with the highest value among other items. The ease with which students access SUAKA-UT based on the responses to the research sample shows that online learning resources are easily accessible to areas in South Sulawesi. Triyono & Tatminingsih (2013) said a difference in the average score between groups that accessed and used SUAKA-UT. This difference in value indicates groups of students who are better and some who are less good at using SUAKA-UT. Student learning activities in accessing learning resources that can be obtained online can help improve mastery of the subject matter. UT's online learning resources include online tutorials, independent online exercises, web supplements, and a digital library. Online tutorials are study assistance services that can contribute to a student's final score added to the final semester exam score. Course enrichment materials using web supplements help improve material mastery with various online activities. They give students various choices or preferences in using learning resources. Preferences for teaching materials can be known by measuring each attribute's usefulness and relative importance in online learning material.

Student satisfaction with online learning resource facilities on the UT website (www.ut.ac.id) is a student's preference for making choices and decisions in utilizing available UT online learning resources. In their research, Rachman, Sukrawan, & Rohendi (2019) found an increase in learning outcomes by using UT's online learning resources. The average n-gain value evidences this at stage three, which reached 0.83 (high criteria), where students were delighted with the application of the blended learning model and enjoyed the learning process. More than that, as many as 78% of students stated that they were interested in and liked the blended learning model, which was characterized by increased motivation, interest, and awareness of students' learning. More specifically, UT-TV and UT Radio are media with learning content that students need and can be accessed by streaming. Ease of access helps students in utilizing these two media as learning resources. In their research, Susanti, Hart, Karyana, & Halimah (2018) found that a well-designed video could increase students' understanding of the informational aspects contained in the video. They included video duration, media form, use of colour, music and illustrations, presenter, and language use. Regarding online tutorials (Tuton), Sugilar & Abzeni (2015) explained that Tutons are UT online learning facilities known, used, and mastered at a very high level by students. Meanwhile, ITV-UT is the least known facility. It contrasts with the current condition where students are very adept at watching live streaming.

Open Educational Resources (OER) has been developed by various universities and organizations worldwide and Indonesia as a learning resource. Harliansyah (2020) argues that the learning process at universities in Indonesia will continue to develop using OER as a learning medium. According to McKerlich, Ives, & McGreal (2013), open educational resource initiatives have been ongoing for more than a decade, and higher education institutions are slowly adopting it. The use and manufacture of OER in all countries is an important aspect needed to improve the quality of education. The availability of quality educational materials readily and widely will change the teaching and learning paradigm and improve the quality of education and knowledge, which holds the key to a country's success. Furthermore, Mtebe & Raisamo (2014) view that open education (OER), which is freely available in the public domain, has the potential to improve the quality of resources. Tanzania, for example, is one country that has adopted and implemented OER as a higher education learning strategy. Meanwhile, in Indonesia, through SUAKA-UT, UT has pioneered the OER model's adoption and utilization.

Student accessibility to learning resources is primarily determined by the ease of students access to available learning resources. Almost all students are proficient and have skills in using technology such as android mobile

phones or laptops with a network to access SUAKA-UT. UT Makassar has conducted training on the use of online learning resources in a hybrid manner (online and offline) on new student study orientation activities and distance learning skills training. This activity aims to achieve student learning success through accessibility or ease of accessing online learning resources provided by UT. In implementing OER at UT, digital libraries or virtual reading rooms have a vital role. Basic materials or digital modules in full text are provided through virtual reading rooms. They are intended to help support student learning activities because they can be accessed anywhere and anytime using a mobile phone or laptop. Through this learning media, students can set the learning atmosphere to meet their planned learning targets. The combination of learning with digital library services for the UT academic community has helped students learn printed and digital basic materials with the same content, thus supporting students to read anywhere and anytime. Meanwhile, independent online practice helps students evaluate themselves through online problem solving with an automatic correction system. Blegur (2020) explains that the evaluation of learning outcomes directly through independent online exercises is objective and transparent, following the final goals that students want to achieve. It encourages students to focus on the final results obtained from their learning activities. This independent exercise also aims to help students discover their success or learning progress after studying a subject matter and prepare themselves for the end-of-semester exams. The question paper in this independent exercise is equipped with instructions containing signs to complete each item and feedback containing explanations for each correct or incorrect answer.

The aforementioned online self-learning facilities provide distance education students with a wealth of experience. The basic assumption of distance education is that all humans can learn independently and grow and develop according to their capacity to direct themselves and adapt to their learning conditions. The experience of using SUAKA-UT learning resources as open education resources (OER) has met the learning needs of UT students very well in remote areas and islands. SUAKA-UT allows individuals to learn according to their learning needs while still doing their jobs and carrying out other life tasks. Learning flexibly, with integrity, and oriented to meet learning needs is done by utilizing online learning resources. This study has shown that the overall score average is 4.10 out of ten SUAKA-UT service items. In general, it can be stated that the respondents strongly agree that the online learning resources provided by UT can meet the learning needs of students and can maximize their independent learning strategies. Student learning by utilizing SUAKA-UT can ultimately form an independent character by utilizing and seeking information and knowledge according to their needs and capacities, with initiatives to support the success of independent learning. It also supports students in applying local wisdom "siri" or "a shy character" if they are not success as it relates to self-esteem in the program and learning achievement.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, student preferences for non-basic education programs at UT Makassar in utilizing SUAKA-UT online learning resources have been excellent. The tendency and preference of students to take advantage of UT's online learning resources have increased significantly. Meanwhile, the ease of access (accessibility) to UT online learning resources (SUAKA-UT) has an excellent assessment by students. Students respond very well to all online learning resources that UT provides to meet their need for helpful learning resources. In the end, to maintain the level of preference and accessibility of students to SUAKA-UT in the excellent assessment category, UT needs to maintain and simultaneously improve the quality of existing services. Eventually, this study recommends that future research can formulate a research model on the effect of preferences and accessibility on improving student achievement.

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